

PUMPING POTENTIAL OF LEFT-VENTRICAL-LIKE FLEXIBLE MATRIX COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

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1 Introduction

Pumps play a vital role in almost every machine including our own body (the heart). Researchers have been assiduously pursuing novel, efficient and powerful pumping action ideas with high Pumping Potential (PP): relative volume reduction engendered by an external stimulus (input stroke),

$$PP = \frac{\Delta V/V_0}{\Delta L/L_0},$$

where

ΔV Volume reduction (ejected volume),

V_0 Initial volume,

ΔL Change in an input characteristic length,

L_0 The initial input characteristic length.

An idea, proposed by Lawrie [1], for generating a high pumping potential has been investigated by Ghoneim. The idea is based on the phenomenon that angle-ply fibrous flexible-matrix-composites (FMC), with $[\pm\theta_f]$ fiber angle orientation, can exhibit an unprecedented high value of the in-plane Poisson's ratio. This high value of the in-plane Poisson's ratio implies that upon stretching an angle-ply FMC axisymmetric shell-of-revolution structure, a substantial reduction of its diameter can be achieved. Consequently, a high PP may be realized. It should be mentioned that Shan et al have applied the phenomenon to produce a novel axial actuator [2]. Ghoneim et al investigated the PP of two angle-ply FMC shell-of-revolution structures under axial loading: hyperbolic [3], and Barrel-shaped [4]. They found out that the concave shape of the hyperbolic structure's surface has a detrimental effect on the PP. And though a high PP is achieved for the barrel-shaped structure, a high axial force is needed to realize this potential, which questions the practicability of the concept. Another

idea is also introduced by Ghoneim [5], which is based on torsional loading of a hyperbolic single-ply FMC structure. The basic idea of the hyperbolic single-ply structure is illustrated in Figure 1. Upon twisting a hyperbolic shell-of-revolution FMC structure with an angle, Φ , under the assumption of rigid fibers and negligible matrix stiffness, the length and the throat diameter decrease, from L_0 to L_1 and from D_0 to D_1 , respectively, rendering a substantial reduction in volume.

Fig 1. Schematic of the deformation and volume reduction of a hyperbolic shell-of-revolution upon twisting.

Recently [6], a revolutionary concept of the heart structure has been introduced by Francisco Torrent-Guasp. The concept advocates that the heart is made of a single band called the helical ventricular myocardial band (HVMB), which twists and loops to form the heart. Figure 2 depicts some of the intermediate dissection steps of a bovine heart undertaken by Torrent-Guasp to unravel the HVMB. Only three steps are shown in the Figure. In the final (third) step, the full extent of the HVMB is displayed. It is divided into two loops: the basal loop, and the apical loop. Each of these two loops is further divided into two segments. The basal loop is divided into the right segment (RS), which concurs with the right ventricle free wall; and the left segment (LS), which coincides with the left ventricle free wall. Similarly, the apical loop can be divided into two segments: the descending (DS) and the ascending (AS) segments. In the first dissection step displayed in Figure 2, the right segment is unwrapped. In the second step, the dissection of the basal loop is completed and the ascending segment is moved aside exposing the near-conical left ventricle (the encircled portion).

Fig. 2 Dissected bovine heart unraveling the HVMB by Torrent-Guasp [6]

In this paper the pumping potential of a near-conical left ventricle-like (LV-like) flexible matrix composite (FMC) structure is investigated in an attempt to unveil any geometric advantages of the “twisting-and-looping” scenario of the heart. In section 2 the idealized model of the LV-like structure under consideration is presented, followed by the experimental and analytical investigation and their results in sections 3 and 4, respectively. In section 5 the results of the investigations are briefed, and a comprehensive discussion of the inter-relation between the “twisting-and-looping” and the PP of the structure is presented.

2 Near-Conical LV-Like Model

A goat’s heart is dissected and unfolded into the HVMB (Figure 3). The shape of the band is recorded. An idealized fiber orientation is assumed to run along the longitudinal axis of the band (principal fiber direction).

Fig. 3 HVMB of the dissected goat’s heart; the outlined area defines the portion considered for the analysis.

Since this study focuses on the pumping potential of a LV-like structure, only the relevant portion of the band is considered (the outlined area in Figure 3). Notice that this portion includes the descending and a portion of the ascending segments. The band is theoretically twisted and looped, using a built-in Matlab program (see Appendix A). Figure 4 shows the considered portion of the band and the assumed fiber orientation adopted for the analysis, together with the final theoretically twisted-and-looped structure: the near-conical LV-like structural model.

Fig. 4 The idealized band and the corresponding near-conical LV-like structure.

A closer look at the generated near-conical LV-like structure is presented in Fig. 5. It is noticed that there are two unique sides of the structure:

1. A descending/ascending side, which is made of two overlapped layers. The fiber orientations of the two layers are different. The two layers constitute an angle-ply laminate, reminiscent of the FMC angle-ply of the barrel-shaped structure studied earlier [4].

Fig. 5 A closer look at the near-conical LV-like structure

2. An ascending side, which is constituted of a single layer and has a predominantly near-circumferential fiber orientation.

It should be pointed out that despite the idealized fiber orientation adopted (Figure 4), the engendered 3D fiber orientation (Figure 5) captures some of the main features of the heart's left ventricle muscle fibers orientation. The two clear ones are [7]:

1. Two crossed fiber population exist in one portion of the ventricle wall as shown in Figure 6 (descending/ascending).

Fig 6 Laminar structure of the heart [8].

2. The populations of the fibers consist of a continuous and helical structure [7].

These structural observations play a role in the pumping action of the LV-like proposed structure and will be revisited later in the Results and Discussion section.

3 Experimental Investigation

3.1 LV-like prototype

It is understood that the ventricle mass is a heterogeneous structure consisting of tissue elements, blood vessels, nerves and interstitial fluid [8]. However, at the macro structural level (Figure 7), the heterogeneous myocardial form is averaged out and becomes consistent with the fibrous composite structural appearance [9, 10]. Consequently, the myocardium mass is presented in this analysis as a fibrous FMC structure.

Fig. 7 Principal muscle fiber orientation as presented by the Auckland “laminar sheet” [10].

For the experimental investigation, a two-part PMC-121/30 Urethane Mold Compound is employed for the matrix, and shape memory alloy (SMA) fibers are applied for the muscle fibers. The flexible actuator wire from DYNALLOY Inc., with a 0.25 mm diameter, was the SMA of choice.

The near-conical LV-like prototype is produced in three main steps:

Fig. 8 The idealized PU/SMA flexible-matrix composite band.

1. The relevant portion of the HVMB, outlined in Figure 3 and presented in Figure 4, is produced using the open mold method. A cavity of the band’s shape is machined into a Teflon block to minimize sticking of the Polyurethane (PU) to the cavity’s surfaces. Guided by appropriate pins, the SMA fibers are placed according to the idealized fiber orientation of the goat’s heart as shown in Figure 8. The two parts of the PU are

mixed well with the appropriate ratio, and poured into the cavity and left for a couple of hours until the mix is partially cured.

2. The partially cured band is twisted and looped to form the near-conical LV-like FMC structure, and left over-night for a complete curing. Since the PU is only partially cured upon twisting and looping, the mating surfaces adhere naturally. At this stage the cured structure is open from both ends (the apex and the base).

Fig. 9 Final conical LV-like structure.

3. A PU base using a secondary open mold is cast to the basal open-end of the conical structure. A cavity having an approximate shape of the basal opening is milled into another Teflon block. The cavity is filled with a bath of polyurethane resin, and the basal end of the near-conical LV-like structure is placed into the cavity (Figure 9), and left till the PU base is completely cured.

3.2 Experimental set-up and results

The SMA fibers of the prototype model of the near – conical LV-like structure are connected to a power supply, and the apex of the conical structure is shoved with a tube extended out from the apex, as shown in Fig. 10. The structure is filled with water till the brim of the apex opening, and the SMA fibers are charged. As the fibers are activated and heated up, they contract causing the structure to deform and to partially collapse in, pumping out water along the extended tube.

Fig. 10 Experimental set-up.

To estimate the PP of the near-conical LV-like FMC structural pump, the SMA is charged with the maximum allowed power, which generates the highest strain, $\epsilon_1 = \Delta L/L_0$, in the SMA without destroying the shape memory of the wires. The volume of the displaced water (ΔV) in the extended tube is measured, and the PP of the proposed composite pump is computed. The results are presented in Table 1.

Parameter	Experimental	ANSYS
ΔV	2.5 cm ³	3.55 cm ³
V_0	50 cm ³	37.73 cm ³
$\Delta L/L_0$	3%	5%
PP	1.67	1.88

Table 1 Experimental and analytical results.

4 Analytical Investigation and Results

The analytical investigation is conducted using ANSYS finite element software. The near-conical LV-like model (Figure 5), generated by the developed Matlab code, is exported to ANSYS. The adopted finite element mesh is displayed in Fig. 11. The PU matrix is modeled with Solid186, and the fibers are modeled with beam189 elements. The base is fixed in all DOF and the model is excited with a 5% thermal strain along the fibers. The material properties adopted for the analysis are given in Table 2. Though linear elastic behavior is adopted

for the analysis, the large deformation analysis is invoked.

Fig. 11 Finite element mesh of the PU matrix (left) and SMA fibers (right).

Material	Property	Value	Unit
SMA	Modulus,	133	GPA
	Poisson's	0.33	
PU	Modulus	20	MPA
	Poisson's	0.48	
Core	Modulus	1	KPA
	Poisson's	0	

Table 2 Material properties adopted for the finite element analysis

To evaluate the volume reduction due to the applied thermal strain, the cavity of the near-conical structure is meshed with brick elements of a virtual material having negligible stiffness and zero Poisson's ratio. The volume reduction of this virtual material (core) upon deformation due to the applied thermal strain is ΔV . The simulation results are displayed, together with the corresponding experimental ones, in Table 1.

5 Results and Discussion

The experimental and analytical investigation of the proposed near-conical LV-like FMC structure yielded a PP of 1.67 and 1.88, respectively. The PP of the different pumping structures in the literature is displayed in Table 3. Though the PP of the proposed near-conical LV-like structure is relatively high,

compared to the cylinder-piston classical pumping structure, it is still well below that of the heart.

Structure	PP
Cylinder-Piston	1.00
LV-like	1.67 -1.88
Hyperbolic	2.59
Heart [11, 12]	3.0 - 4.5
Barrel Shaped	10.33

Table 3 PP of some FMC structures.

Revisiting the fiber orientation of the proposed structure (Figure 5); there are two main orientations, which exist in the real heart: Anti-symmetric angle-ply orientation in the ascending/descending side, and predominantly circumferential in the thin side of the structure. It can be shown that for a FMC conical structure with an angle ply fiber orientation, $1 \leq PP \leq 2$ (Appendix B). Consequently, the resulting values of PP for the proposed structure, with apex angle $\alpha \cong 15^\circ$, range between 1-2 is normal. Therefore, this investigation concludes that the twisting-and-looping of a band with an idealized fiber orientation, along the main axis of the band (principal fiber direction), is not sufficient to produce the high PP ($PP = 3 - 4.5$) of the heart. And the question remains: "Why twisting and looping?"

There are three other factors that need to be further investigated and may explain the above daunting question:

1. An idealized fiber angle orientation has been adopted for this analysis and a more accurate angle orientation is needed. Ghoneim [4] showed that the angle orientation plays a crucial role in the pumping potential of the barrel-shaped angle-ply FMC structure.
2. The torsional effect has not been emphasized in this study, though it has been suggested that it plays an important role in the pumping action of the heart [12].
3. The thickening effect: The walls of the heart experiences a considerable thickening which further enhances the ejection and pumping efficiency of the heart [13].

These factors will be the subjects of future study.

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Appendices:

A. Rolling a plane surface into a conical surface

The following analysis explains how to roll a flat plane surface into a cone with a known apex angle. As shown in Fig A1, we place the flat surface on the YZ plane. The target cone is placed such that the Z-axis coincides with one of the cone's side (slant) line, and that the axis of the cone, defined by the unit vector w , lies in the XZ plane.

Let us assume a generic point on the flat plane, A_1 , which is to be moved to the corresponding point A_3 on the surface of the target cone. Also, let us denote R_1 and R_3 as the vector representations of points A_1 and A_3 , respectively. The transformation of point A_1 to A_3 is accomplished via two consecutives rotations of the vector R_1 . The first rotation, which renders R_2 , is achieved by rotating the vector R_1 about the X-axis with an angle Ψ . In the second rotation, the vector R_2 is rotated about the unit vector of the axis of the cone w by an angle, θ , such that $R\Psi = r \theta$, where R is the magnitude of the vector R_i ($i = 1, 2$ or 3) and r is the radius of the cone at the intermediate point A_2 (Fig. A1). Note that $r = R \sin \alpha$, where α is the apex angle of the cone.

Fig. A1 Schematic illustration of the rolling process of a flat plane into a conical surface.

It can be shown that the transformation matrix T , which rotates R_2 about w producing R_3 , is given by

$$R_3 = T \cdot R_2,$$

where $T(w, \theta) =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} w_x w_x vc + c & w_y w_x vc - w_z s & w_z w_x vc + w_y s \\ w_x w_y vc + w_z s & w_y w_y vc + c & w_z w_y vc - w_x s \\ w_x w_z vc - w_y s & w_y w_z vc + w_x s & w_z w_z vc + c \end{bmatrix}$$

with $c = \cos\theta$, $s = \sin\theta$, and $vc = 1 - \cos\theta$. The angle cosines w_x , w_y and w_z are of the unit vectors w ; that is, $w = (w_x, w_y, w_z)^T$.

It should be also mentioned that r , while generating the near-cone LV-like structure, is increased in proportion to θ , such that the incremental increase in r every complete revolution ($\theta = 2\pi$) equals to the thickness of the flat plate. This way, the excess portion of the flat plane with $\theta > 2\pi$ wraps perfectly well over the previously rolled portions with $\theta < 2\pi$; that is, without any gaps between the two mating surfaces.

B. Estimation of the pumping potential of a conical surface

Let us assume a cone of radius r and apex angle α , we will find the volume change, ΔV , due to a change of the length of an input characteristic line on the cone's surface, which makes an angle θ with the slant height, s .

Figure 1B Parameters of the conical surface.

The volume, V , of the cone is

$$V(r, s) = \frac{1}{3} \pi r^2 h = \frac{1}{3} \pi r^2 \sqrt{s^2 - r^2} \quad (1B)$$

Where, r is the radius, h is the height and s is the slant height. Differentiating with respect to the two variable r and s , we get

$$\Delta V = \frac{2}{3} \pi r h \left(\frac{s^2 - 1.5r^2}{s^2 - r^2} \right) \Delta r + \frac{1}{3} \pi r^2 \left(\frac{s}{h} \right) \Delta s,$$

Upon dividing by the volume (equation 1B), we get the expression for the volume reduction ratio:

$$\frac{\Delta V}{V} = 2 \left(\frac{s^2 - 1.5r^2}{s^2 - r^2} \right) \frac{\Delta r}{r} + \left(\frac{s}{h} \right)^2 \frac{\Delta s}{s} \quad (2B)$$

Let us introduce the following normal components of the strain: The tangential strain $\varepsilon_\theta = \Delta r/r$, the slant strain (along s) $\varepsilon_s = \Delta s/s$, the fiber's strain (along the characteristic length) $\varepsilon_l = \Delta L/L$, and ε_m normal to the characteristic line and along the surface of the cone. L is the length of the characteristic line. Applying the standard strain transformation, we have,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \varepsilon_{s\theta} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} m^2 & n^2 & 2nm \\ n^2 & m^2 & -2mn \\ -mn & mn & m^2 - n^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_l \\ \varepsilon_m \\ \varepsilon_{lm} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3B)$$

where $m = \cos\theta$, $n = \sin\theta$, and $\varepsilon_{s\theta}$ and ε_{lm} are the corresponding shear strain components. We assume that the Poisson's effect is negligible, then when ε_l is imposed, we may impose $\varepsilon_m = \varepsilon_{lm} = 0$. Consequently, from (3B):

$$\varepsilon_\theta = \frac{\Delta r}{r} = \frac{\Delta L}{L} \sin^2 \theta, \text{ and } \varepsilon_s = \frac{\Delta s}{s} = \frac{\Delta L}{L} \cos^2 \theta$$

Substituting into (2B), after some manipulation:

$$PP = \frac{\Delta V}{V} / \frac{\Delta L}{L} = (2 - \tan^2 \alpha) \sin^2 \theta + (\sec^2 \alpha) \cos^2 \theta$$

Figure 2B PP of the conical structure

Figure 2B displays PP versus θ for different values of the apex angle, α . Notice that values of $\alpha > 45^\circ$ are impractical for pumping, since the flexure stiffness of the cone's surface considerably abates and, therefore its pumping ability deteriorates as well. For values $\alpha < 45^\circ$, PP is confined to the range (1~2). It should be pointed out that this analysis is based on small displacements.